

STUDENT VOLUNTEERISM AS EXPERIENCED BY THE CAMPUS MINISTRY IMPLEMENTING ARMS (CMIA) VOLUNTEERS OF NDMU

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Student Volunteerism as Experienced by the Campus Ministry Implementing Arms (CMIA) Volunteers of NDMU

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Abstract

This research is a single holistic case study that investigated the experiences of student volunteers working with Notre Dame of Marbel University's (NDMU) Campus Ministry Implementing Arms (CMIA). It looked into the experience of non-RE student volunteers at various ministries such as Catechism, Altar Servers Ministry, Sacred Arts Ministry, Lectors Ministry, and the Saint Cecilia's Choir, which are all under CMIA. The study revealed that the CMIA volunteers see student volunteerism as the willingness to offer genuine service, being involved in diverse activities as a helping hand, being responsible with time, building good interpersonal relationships, enhancing self-esteem, and being responsive to the community needs. Time constraints, demotivation, and poor volunteer participation, in addition to uncertainty in task selection, are some of the challenges that CMIA volunteers face. As a result, these volunteers use different coping strategies, such as managing time effectively, prioritizing needs and relevant tasks, exercising foresight, and collaborative assistance. The study's findings emphasize the importance of understanding the intricate nature of student volunteering with all its challenges and ways of overcoming them; this information may help those planning to work as volunteers in CMIA to better put themselves in their role, balance other responsibilities with volunteer roles, and develop themselves both socially and personally. The study underscores the need for supportive measures from CMIA coordinators and administrators, such as targeted training programs and proactive strategies to address common challenges. By implementing these recommendations, NDMU can enhance the volunteer experience, promoting growth and success for future CMIA student-volunteers.

Keywords: *student volunteerism, CMIA volunteers, coping strategies, challenges, community service*

Introduction

Volunteerism is a personal investment made by those who prefer to devote their time and effort to giving services to the community or aiding the less fortunate without expecting recompense (Clary & Snyder, 1999). This spirit of volunteerism is an individual endeavor and can manifest within organizations, creating a powerful force for community improvement (Alavi et al., 2022). One such embodiment of organized volunteerism is the Campus Ministry Implementing Arms (CMIA) volunteers of Notre Dame of Marbel University (NDMU). The CMIA has five ministries, namely, Catechism, Altar Server Ministry, Sacred Arts Ministry, Lectors Ministry, and Saint Cecilia's Choir. These are religious ministries, and most of the people working in them are Religious Education students because it belongs to their duty, but some volunteers are non-RE and still give their best in the ministries they joined. By exploring the experiences of these non-RE student volunteers, valuable insights were gained into student volunteerism, challenges, coping strategies, and the overall impact of their volunteer service despite their status as non-RE members of the aforementioned ministries while juggling with their academics.

Research indicates that engagement in volunteer activities positively influences college students' social and moral development, contributing to their overall moral identity (Chen & Liang, 2020). Moreover, student volunteers often engage in various sectors, including community development and education, reaping intrinsic and extrinsic rewards (Mustafa et al., 2020). These student-volunteerism studies focus on the effects of student-volunteerism on the students, yet still limited readings focus on the student-volunteers who have joined two or more organizations or groups while taking into account their academics. There are also limited readings on the student-volunteers who chose to volunteer in religious ministries which is why the researchers came up to dig on student volunteerism as experienced by the student-volunteers of religious ministries at Notre Dame of Marbel University.

By examining the diverse aspects of student volunteerism within the context of CMIA volunteers at NDMU, this research sought to provide a comprehensive understanding of the valuable experiences associated with the service rendered by the CMIA volunteers. Learning from the experiences of these student volunteers not only contributed to their personal and social development but also shed light on potential areas of improvement for institutions and organizations facilitating volunteer programs. This exploration is essential for creating effective interventions, fostering a supportive environment for student volunteers, and maximizing the positive impact of their contributions to the community.

Research Questions

This study explored student-volunteerism as experienced by CMIA volunteers of NDMU. Specifically, it answered the following:

1. How may student volunteerism be described as experienced by CMIA volunteers?
2. What are the challenges encountered on student-volunteerism by the CMIA volunteers?
3. What are the coping strategies employed by CMIA volunteers to address the challenges?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a research design centered on a case study, specifically employing the methodology of a single holistic case study. A holistic case study focuses on a single unit of analysis, providing a comprehensive description. In this study, the focus is on a single organization: Campus Ministry Implementing Arms (CMIA), which includes five ministries (Catechist, Sacred Arts, St. Cecilia's Choir, Altar Servers, and Lectors). The participants in the study are non-Religious Education student-volunteers who are members of two or more of these ministries.

The selection of a holistic case study was pertinent for investigating the experiences of these student-volunteers. The overarching purpose was to furnish a thorough understanding of the case in its entirety. To gather relevant data and address inquiries related to the case, the researchers employed interview guide questionnaires. This procedure involved using a set of organized and standardized questions during interviews with the participants. The aim was to ensure consistency and uniformity in the data collection process across all participants, enabling a comprehensive exploration of the case at hand.

Participants

The participants of this study were NDMU CMIA non-RE major volunteers. The inclusion criteria prepared by the researchers for selecting participants of the study were as follows: they had to be NDMU graduates or current bonafide students of Notre Dame of Marbel University who are or were members of the CMIA for at least two years, and they had to be members of at least two ministries such as catechism, altar servers, sacred arts, lectors, and Saint Cecilia's Choir. Additionally, they must have been willing to participate and be interviewed.

There were three participants who showed their willingness to participate in this study, and they were interviewed. Two (2) of the participants were already graduates, one was from the College of Business Administration and was a member of the Altar Servers and Sacred Arts Ministry. The other participant is an engineer from the College of Engineering, Architecture, and Computing and a member of the Saint Cecilia's Choir and Sacred Arts Ministry. The third participant was, at the conduct of the study. A third (3rd) year student from the College of Arts and Sciences and a member of Lectors, Altar Server, and Sacred Arts Ministries.

Instrument

The research instrument used by the researcher was an interview guide. The questions were presented, checked, and validated by the panel members and the adviser. It is composed of questions to be answered by the participants subjectively.

Moreover, researchers also prepared probing questions related to the general questions to be answered by the participants to gain important insights and information. After the panel members and the adviser validated the questions, they were endorsed by the panelists and the adviser to the College of Education Dean, who approved the researchers to gather the data.

Procedure

In conducting the study, the researchers first created a request letter approved by their research adviser and the Dean of the College of Education before forwarding it to the participants. Second, the interview guide consisted of eight major and follow-up questions to gather information.

After receiving suggestions, the researchers revised the interview guide. They then went to the respondents' area and sought an approval letter from them. Upon approval, the respondents gave their consent to conduct the interview. Third, the researchers conducted one-on-one interviews with the participants. Various tools were used, such as a voice recorder, a pen, and a notebook, with the participants' permission to ensure their privacy.

The interviews were conducted based on the participants' availability and were completed in two days. P1 was interviewed in the third week of June 2024 for 10 minutes. On the same date as P1, P2 was interviewed for 12 minutes. P3 was interviewed on the 11th of June 2024 for 8 minutes.

During the interviews, the researchers used two cellphones and a sheet of paper to record the participants' experiences. The questions were translated into the participants' comfortable language. Lastly, after the interviews were conducted, the researchers transcribed the audio recordings into text verbatim. After transcribing, the researchers used thematic analysis to interpret the data.

Data Analysis

The researchers used thematic analysis with dataset analysis to analyze the data process to better suit specific research needs or contexts. This included significant statements, formulated meanings, concepts, and categories/themes. From the transcription, the responses were selected and categorized based on the statement of the problem (SOP). The researchers then derived concepts from their significant statements. After formulating these, they developed themes from the concepts. To extract themes for each SOP, an in-depth analysis was conducted. The researchers created a table where significant statements, concepts, and themes were categorized to answer the SOP. They closely examined the data to identify common themes, ideas, and patterns of meaning that recurred. Since thematic analysis

involves analyzing qualitative data, it was applied to a set of texts such as interviews or transcripts.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical considerations of the researchers were followed to ensure that each participant was informed and free to choose whether to participate or decline the interview. The researchers applied the code of ethics in conducting the research, prioritizing the dignity of the participants. Moreover, the participants were informed about the interview protocol and the study to be conducted. The researchers stand obligated to protect and secure the confidentiality of their participants, ensuring the anonymity of their identity and responses in this study. In addition, the researchers conducted this study in-person, and the use of phones or any device for the recording process was included. With certainty, the participants were informed that what transpired in the discussion will remain confidential and secure.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the findings of the study based on the interview with the participants. This chapter consists of several tables that show the themes of the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of Notre Dame of Marbel University (NDMU) Campus Ministry Implementing Arms (CMIA) volunteers.

Table 1. *Student-Volunteerism as Described and Experienced by CMIA Student-Volunteers*

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Concepts	Categories/Themes
P1: "As a CMIA volunteer I describe student volunteerism as a tool to identify students who are willing to offer or give themselves willingly or genuinely to serve for the school or especially for God"	Volunteerism as a way to identify and encourage students to willingly serve the school and God.	Willingness to serve Genuineness in service	Willingness to offer genuine service
P1: "my experience on student volunteerism varies from being a member in a choir such as a Saint Cecilia's Choir and as a helping hand of sacred arts in their activities such as helping, preparing them for their activities."	Volunteerism is the involvement in various activities such as being a part of the choir and assisting in sacred arts, providing support and preparation for events.	Involving in diverse activities as a helping hand and supporter	Being involved in diverse activities as a helping hand
P2: "Sa pagdescribe ko sang student volunteerism, aside from being a student I still have much time; may ara para ko sang time para sa other things nga dapat ko obrahon pero ginlaan ko ang iban ko nga oras sa pagiging altar server or sa pagiging volunteer sa school."	Balancing student responsibilities with volunteer work, dedicating time to serve as an altar server or volunteer.	Balancing responsibilities as a student Dedicating time for service	Being responsible with time
P2: "maka socialize ka sa iban nga mga ministry"	Socializing with different ministries	Socializing	Building good interpersonal relationship
P3: "ako abi nga tao kay di ko kaayo very social na tao so, siguro ang na acquire ko na skill kay ng mas maging outgoing kag ng mag interact pa sa iban nga tao."	Developing social skills and becoming more outgoing through volunteering.	Becoming more outgoing	
P3: "during sa time nga naga volunteer ko damo ko may na meet nga mga tao na same man sa akon na volunteer. Dira na time kay ahm nakabuuild ko sang friendship sa ila kag nakapangita ko sang tao na ng makarelata ko."	Building friendships and finding relatable people through volunteering.	Building relationships Finding relatable peers Building confidence	Enhancing self-esteem
P2: "ma enhance ang imo nga confidence during volunteering times."	enhancing confidence through volunteering.		
P1: "it greatly affected my academic and personal growth by giving a positive impact in both of my academic and personal growth. It boosted my self-esteem and my confidence. It challenges my confidence to face different kinds of people or faces upon singing or serving."	Volunteering positively impacts academic and personal growth, boosting self-esteem and confidence	Enhancing confidence and self-esteem	
P3: "when my ara nga activities na need ang mga CMIA Volunteers kay ng naga respond kami sa kung ano ang need"	Responding to the needs of the community through volunteer activities.	Responding to community needs	Being responsive to the community needs

The Description of NDMU CMIA Volunteers' experiences on Student Volunteerism

Willingness to Offer Genuine Service

The Notre Dame of Marbel University Campus Ministry Implementing Arms (NDMU CMIA) volunteers are tasked to do things under the various ministries. Those jobs particularly require a willingness to lend time and service as mentioned by Participant 1, "As a CMIA volunteer, I describe student volunteerism as a tool to identify students who are willing to offer or give themselves willingly or

genuinely to serve for the school or especially for God."

This viewpoint aligns with one of the theories provided in this research, the altruism theory by Auguste Comte (1851), which entails behaving with a genuine interest in the welfare of others or the context of this research – student-volunteerism in various ministries. Additionally, the study of Ozorak (2003) states that the intrinsic motivation to volunteer and personal relationship with God are key predictors of college students' intention to repeat volunteer service and their likelihood to volunteer again. As is commonly known, intrinsic motivation comes from within, and this is truly anchored to the giving of genuine service because of the willingness derived from one's own intention—an intrinsic motivation.

Being Involved in Diverse Activities as a Helping Hand

Volunteers play a crucial role within the NDMU CMIA, significantly contributing to the activities of the five ministries: catechism, altar serving, sacred arts, lectors, and choir. Participant 1 exemplifies this by sharing, "My experience on student volunteerism varies from being a member in a choir such as Saint Cecilia's Choir and as a helping hand of sacred arts in their activities such as helping, preparing them for their activities." This statement underscores the diverse ways volunteers serve, mainly through participation in multiple ministries, embodying the essence of being a helping hand.

Hodgkinson (2003) supports this notion by highlighting that volunteering greatly contributes to community and social development, fostering social solidarity and enhancing the quality of life. This alignment with Participant 1's experience as a volunteer in multiple ministries emphasizes the holistic contribution of volunteers to the CMIA. This illustrates that volunteers serve as a helping hand across various activities and ministries, reinforcing their integral role in enhancing community cohesion and support.

Being Responsible with Time

Being a student and, at the same time, a volunteer of two or more ministries or organizations is truly a battle a student-volunteer needs to face every day or every time the task is given at the same time. The statement of Participant 2 of this paper highlights this by saying, "Sa pagdescribe ko sang student volunteerism, aside from being a student I still have much time; may ara para ko sang time para sa other things nga dapat ko obrahon pero ginlaan ko ang iban ko nga oras sa pagiging altar server or sa pagiging volunteer sa school." The participant's experience shows that student-volunteerism is about being responsible with time. Student-volunteers truly experience this in their volunteerism work, much more that they belong in two or more ministries or organizations.

In light of this, a literature review by AmeriCorps authored by Spinney and Clinton (2024) supports this, as their article highlights that volunteers often develop strong organizational and time management skills due to their varied responsibilities and the need to balance their volunteer activities with personal and professional commitments. These skills are essential in ensuring that volunteers can effectively manage their time, meet deadlines, and fulfill their duties reliably. With this, student-volunteerism can be described as hitting two or more birds with one stone—a student-volunteer who needs to be responsible with time management because of being a student and having two or more ministries or organizations inside the Institution.

Building Good Interpersonal Relationships

Volunteerism allows individuals to meet other people and work on a specific task. With that, it is inevitable to work with different people, create relationships with them along the way. This is true with the description of student-volunteerism of the participants of this study. Participant 2 highlighted this description by saying, "Maka socialize ka sa iban nga mga ministry." Participant 3 also shared his statement, "Ako abi nga tao kay di ko kaayo very social na tao so, siguro ang na acquire ko na skill kay ng mas maging outgoing kag ng mag interact pa sa iban nga tao." He also added, "during sa time nga naga volunteer ko damo ko may na meet nga mga tao na same man sa akon na volunteer. Dira na time kay ahm nakabuild ko sang friendship sa ila kag nakapangita ko sang tao na ng makarelake ko." These statements from the participants describe that student-volunteerism is an avenue for building good interpersonal relationships.

In a related context, the study of Hoi and Yin (2023) also highlights that volunteering can lead to improved interpersonal relationships and creating a new worldview among university students. With the interpersonal relationship being said, genuinely volunteering in organizations and ministries has an impact on making good relationships with other people. Additionally, the statement is also supported by the paper of Wrench, Punyanunt-Carter, and Thweatt (2020), which highlights that volunteerism is a powerful avenue for developing communication skills and building interpersonal relationships. Lastly, the social exchange theory of George Homans (1958) is highly applicable in this context as it highlights that volunteer work or activities done by volunteers are about the anticipation of obtaining social benefits in return, which in this context is the building of interpersonal relationships. With the description by the participant, the studies mentioned, and the theory that was applied, student-volunteerism truly helps build good interpersonal relationships.

Enhancing self-esteem

Volunteering in various ministries, groups, communities, or organizations exposes one to many situations. This exposure or work leads to enhancing self-esteem according to the participants of the study. This was highlighted in the statements of Participant 2, who testified "Ma enhance ang imo nga confidence during volunteering times." Participant 1 also highlighted, "It greatly affected my academic and

personal growth by positively impacting my academic and personal growth. It boosted my self-esteem and my confidence. It challenges my confidence to face different kinds of people or faces upon singing or serving." With the experiences shared by the participants, student-volunteerism truly enhances their self-esteem.

With this context, the study of Wrench, Punyanunt-Carter, and Thweatt (2020) highlighted that student-volunteerism provides multiple avenues for enhancing self-esteem through skill development, social connections, recognition, and personal growth. These experiences collectively contribute to a stronger, more positive self-image and higher self-esteem. Additionally, the theory of George Homans (1958) is also related on this. This theory sheds light on the idea that volunteer activities have social or personal benefits in return—which, in relation to this context, is the improvement of the self-esteem of the volunteer. The statements of the participant that resulted from their experiences, the theory, and the study mentioned above are parallel, validating that student-volunteerism truly is a gateway for enhancing self-esteem.

Being Responsive to the Community Needs

Volunteering in various works of the ministries or groups one is in requires being responsive. When the task calls volunteers to respond, they must consider it. With this, Participant 3 shared "When my ara nga activities na need ang mga CMIA Volunteers kay ng naga to respond kami sa kung ano ang need." In response to the need mentioned by the volunteer, making himself responsive to those certain needs is what student-volunteerism means.

In this context, the study of Writers (2020) highlights this, which states that student volunteerism is greatly enhanced by making oneself available and managing time effectively. It highlights the importance of making oneself available and responsive for various activities, emphasizing the significant role of time management and availability in successful volunteer engagements. With this, self-availability anchored to being responsive to the needs of the community, as described by the student-volunteers, is highly related to student-volunteerism as it mainly encapsulates the response of the volunteers while doing work or working on the task.

Table 2. *The Challenges Encountered by the CMIA Student-volunteer*

<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meaning</i>	<i>Concepts</i>	<i>Categories/Themes</i>
P1: "The obstacles that I face as a CMIA volunteer in our ministries is time."	Time is a primary challenge faced by CMIA volunteers.	Time as an obstacle to volunteer work	Time constraint
P2: "Sa obstacles, kis-a oras kay ti may ara sang other priorities so kinanglan mo pud nga mag laan sang time sa pagiging volunteer kag may ara gid sang times gis a nga mapapili ka gid kung diin ang mas importante."	Time and other priorities are significant obstacles.	Conflict of time and other priorities	Instances of being demotivated
P3: "May ara lang nga mga time gid na kung kis-a ahm nagasabay sa kung busy sa academics."	Balancing volunteer work with academic responsibilities, sometimes causing conflict.	Conflict of time in academic and volunteer work	
P1: "It makes spirit of volunteerism ignite more or burn brighter because it gives me challenge to find ways in order for me to volunteer it is like, I want to serve and there is this the devil will find a way to make me not give service."	Challenges in volunteerism are related to motivation to serve.	Losing sense of motivation	Being affected by the poor participation of some volunteers
P3: "kis-a abi gamay lang ang mag volunteer or magparticipate bala haw so, ng nagawonder ko kung ano ba ang pilion ko sa adlaw nga na kung sa ano ko nga part magbulig so siguro amunang mga obstacle ng ana face ko."	Experiencing difficulty due to poor volunteer participation.	Poor participation of some volunteers	Uncertainty in task selection
	Uncertainty about where to help and which task to prioritize.	Problem in deciding which task to fulfill	

The Challenges Encountered by the CMIA Student-Volunteers

Time Constraint

Student-volunteers can experience challenges while volunteering in various group, ministries, and organizations inside the institution. This is true in the statements of the participants of the study. Participant 1 stated, "The obstacles that I face as a CMIA volunteer in our ministries is time." Participant 2 also shared, "Sa obstacles, kis-a oras kay ti may ara sang other priorities so kinanglan mo pud nga mag laan sang time sa pagiging volunteer kag may ara gid sang times gis a nga mapapili ka gid kung diin ang mas importante." Lastly, Participant 3 also highlighted that, "May ara lang nga mga time gid na kung kis-a ahm nagasabay sa kung busy sa academics." With the statements of these three participants, it can be said concluded that time constraint is one of the many challenges they experience in student-volunteerism.

The statements mentioned above are supported by the study entitled Attributes Influencing College Students' Participation in Volunteering by Yin and Won (2011). This study notes that lack of time is one of the primary barriers to student volunteering. This constraint often prevents students from engaging in regular volunteer activities, thereby affecting their overall contribution and

experience in volunteer programs. With the statement provided and the study mentioned, time constraint is a major challenge for student-volunteers, impacting their ability to participate consistently and effectively in volunteer activities.

Instances of Being Demotivated

Responding to the need of various groups and ministries is sometimes demotivating for some volunteers, and it was highlighted by Participant 1 of the study who states that, "It makes spirit of volunteerism ignite more or burn brighter because it gives me challenge to find ways in order for me to volunteer it is like, I want to serve and there is this the devil will find a way to make me not give service." The devil, as mentioned by the participant, is the main challenge that he is experiencing which primary means being demotivated at some ways. Being demotivated is also caused by being overwhelmed with task, burnout, or just simply lack of motivation do task.

Instances of demotivation present a significant challenge in student volunteerism, affecting both the sustainability and effectiveness of volunteer efforts. This challenge is also stated in the study of Morse et al. (2020) which highlights that a key issue in being demotivated is burnout, which is often arising from excessive demands and a lack of recognition or support. With the statement of the participant as well as the supporting study, it is clear that instances of being demotivated is a serious challenge faced by student-volunteers or various organizations, and, in this context, the ministries.

Being Affected by the Poor Participation of Some Volunteers

It is inevitable that in a specific volunteer group, some might have poor performance some affecting the performance of other students as well. Participant 3 of the study give statement on this saying, "Kis-a abi gamay lang ang mag volunteer or magparticipate bala haw so, ng nagawonder ko kung ano ba ang pilion ko sa adlaw nga na kung sa ano ko nga part magbulig so siguro amunang mga obstacle ng ana face ko." With the poor performance of the other volunteers, Participant 3 experienced reading to juggle responsibilities their – which explains how other performance affects the other volunteers.

The study of Wondimu and Admas (2024), notes that low engagement levels among volunteers can lead to feelings of frustration and demotivation among those who are actively participating. This study, as conducted on the motivation and engagement of student-volunteers at the University of Gondar, found that a lack of active participation from fellow volunteers can diminish the overall experience and satisfaction of student-volunteers, thereby affecting their willingness to continue volunteering. With this being shown, the statement and the study is highly parallel to each, which highlights the common challenge and experience of the student volunteers which is the instances of being demotivated.

Uncertainty in Task Selection

As what was stated in our inclusion criteria, the participants were members of two or more organizations or ministry. This multi-tasking done in multiple ministries offers uncertainty in task selection or what ministry should be given thorough attention. As mentioned by the Participant 3 of this study, "Kis-a abi gamay lang ang mag volunteer or magparticipate bala haw so, ng nagawonder ko kung ano ba ang pilion ko sa adlaw nga na kung sa ano ko nga part magbulig so siguro amunang mga obstacle ng ana face ko." In juggling with multiple ministries, the participant highlighted that he experienced having uncertainty in which task to select first or what thing should be given importance.

In this context, the study of Qiao and Zhang (2020) is in support to the statement mentioned. This study highlights that in student-volunteerism, one significant challenge is the uncertainty in task selection due to involvement in multiple organizations. This challenge is often a result of overlapping commitments and the varied nature of tasks within different organizations, which can lead to confusion and inefficiency. A study on international event volunteers in China highlights that students often face difficulties in aligning their tasks and responsibilities when volunteering for multiple events or organizations, which can negatively impact their overall experience and effectiveness. The statement provided by the participant and the study is parallel on the concept the uncertainty of task selection.

Table 3. *The Coping Strategies Employed by the CMIA Student-Volunteers*

<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meaning</i>	<i>Concepts</i>	<i>Categories/Themes</i>
P1: "So, the strategies I personally use to cope with those obstacles is that I manage my time well, I make sure that before I serve or before I will do service, I make sure that my academics are finished or in a good condition."	Manages time effectively balance academics and service.	Management of time Balancing time for academics and service	Managing time effectively
P3: "para makacope ko amuto gani kay eh manage ang time kag ng isipon gid kung ano ang imo priority."	Coping the difficulty experienced by managing time	Using time efficiently	
P1: " I have acquired effective coping mechanism from other CMIA volunteers prioritizing tasks and doing it efficiently, by maximizing energy on those that is more relevant or relevant to my priorities."	Learning from others, to prioritizing and maximize energy on relevant tasks. Prioritizing tasks based on the	Prioritizing and maximizing energy on relevant task	Prioritizing needs and relevant tasks

P3: "Ginasisip ko nalang kung ano ang dapat ko unahon eh prioritize kung kunwari kung may ara man sa amuni nga ministry kag sa piyak mas gamay lang sila didto anay ko magbulig ng daw amo sina."	needs of different ministries, especially where there are fewer volunteers.	Prioritizing needed tasks Assessing the needs of different ministries	
P2: "Sa iban nga mga strategies, makita ko as a president, ma observe ko man sa iban ko nga upod medyo nabudlayan gid sila manage sang ila nga time. Maobserve ko lang saila, gina inform ko na daan sila ahead of time kag sila mismo, gina excuse na nila ila sarili sa mga teacher or ila nga mga communities para makaattend sila sang any activities nga gina patagayon sang ila ministry."	Observing time management issues in peers, informs them in advance, and advises them to seek permission from teachers/community to attend activities.	Advanced information Seeking permission	Exercising foresight
P3: "ang na acquire ko na coping mechanism sa ila is that maghambal sa ila na kung hindi ko makalakat"	Coping mechanism involves open communication	Communicating Openly	Collaborative Assistance
P3: "Since damo man ko na upod na volunteer naga ask man ko sa ila na kung sino pwede magbulig para mag gaan lang ang trabaho."	Asking fellow volunteers for help to lighten the workload.	Seeking help from others	
P3: "like kung ang iban hindi man makalakat kay ang magbuliganay lang amu siguro na magbuliganay lang para matapos namon ang dapat ubrahon."	mutual assistance among volunteers to complete tasks.	Giving mutual assistance	

The Coping Strategies Employed by the CMIA Volunteers to Address the Challenges

Management Time Effectively

One of the coping strategy employed in the challenges experienced by the volunteers is the management of time effectively. This is true to the statements provided by the participants of the study. Participant 1 mentioned that, "So, the strategies I personally use to cope with those obstacles is that I manage my time well, I make sure that before I serve or before I will do service, I make sure that my academics are finished or in a good condition." Participant 3 also added significant statements that is anchored on this coping strategy "Para makacope ko amuto gani kay eh manage ang time kag ng isipon gid kung ano ang imo priority."

The statement mentioned above particularly management of time effectively, is supported by the study of Takács et al. (2021). This study highlights that for students engaged in volunteerism, time management is particularly crucial as it allows them to contribute meaningfully to their volunteer work while maintaining their academic performance. This balance not only enhances their personal growth and satisfaction but also positively impacts their mental health and resilience in the face of stress. With this, managing time effectively is one of the strategies that must be employed in volunteer work as it is proven to affect positively the volunteers in their volunteer work.

Prioritizing Needs and Relevant Tasks

The participants of this study were members of two or more ministries and they have employed coping strategies that focused on prioritizing needs and relevant tasks. Participant 1 stated that, " I have acquired effective coping mechanism from other CMIA volunteers prioritizing tasks and doing it efficiently, by maximizing energy on those that is more relevant or relevant to my priorities." The Participant 3 also mentioned, "Ginasisip ko nalang kung ano ang dapat ko unahon eh prioritize kung kunwari kung may ara man sa amuni nga ministry kag sa piyak mas gamay lang sila didto anay ko magbulig ng daw amo sina." The statements of the participants are directly focused on prioritizing needs and relevant tasks which provides positive effects in volunteerism.

In this context, the study of Melhem and Melhem (2023) is in support. The study shows that task prioritization is important for better performance in the organization. With this being stated, task prioritization is a great way to cope with the challenges faced the student-volunteers who are members of multiple ministries.

Exercising Foresight

In times of uncertainty and activities that might happen within the organization or the ministries, exercising foresight is significant, and it was mentioned and highlighted by the Participant 2 of this study, "Sa iban nga mga strategies, makita ko as a president, ma observe ko man sa iban ko nga upod medyo nabudlayan gid sila manage sang ila nga time. Maobserve ko lang saila, gina inform ko na daan sila ahead of time kag sila mismo, gina excuse na nila ila sarili sa mga teacher or ila nga mga communities para makaattend sila sang any activities nga gina patagayon sang ila ministry." Participant 3 also added, that "ang na acquire ko na coping mechanism sa ila is that maghambal sa ila na kung hindi ko makalakat." With the statements mentioned by the student volunteers, exercising foresight is a great help.

clearly represents how the student volunteer inductively approaches their passion for volunteerism, from experiencing student-volunteerism, challenges, and coping mechanisms all within the campus ministry.

The experiences of CMIA student-volunteers at NDMU did much to enlighten about student volunteerism, showing its enriching and challenging dimensions. There have been a number of major insights and realizations that emerged from this research on the nature of student volunteerism, the obstacles, and coping strategies of volunteers.

Basically, the motivation for intrinsic student volunteerism that the researchers learned from these volunteers is the desire to render real service. The desire strongly links or relates to intrinsic motivation and sincerely connects the concern of their fellow beings' good. Their desire to serve the school and the spiritual community, repeatedly stated or in some cases indicated by the participants in this study, confirms altruism theory and supports the argument that real volunteerism is inspired by a desire to give or make a positive contribution that comes from the heart.

Another realization from this study involves the diversity of volunteer activities and multifaceted roles that students undertake. Such diversity is manifested by involvement in various ministries, such as catechism, altar serving, sacred arts, lectors, choir, among others, underlining that breadth of volunteering. This diversity not only improves community and social development but also gives rise to social solidarity and enhances quality of life within the university community. The study underlines the fact that, at a larger level, volunteers have holistic contributions across multiple ministries.

The researchers then identified that among the essential skills required by student volunteers is time management. According to participants, effective time management is necessary in balancing their academic responsibilities with volunteer commitments. Researchers realized that being responsible with their time enables volunteers to be reliable and perform tasks without affecting their academic performance. This insight supports literature emphasizing that organizational and time management skills are very vital in volunteerism.

The study also established that student volunteerism is a significant way of building good interpersonal relationships. Since volunteers usually work in groups, social connections and friendships therefore automatically develop. It is this social aspect of volunteerism that adds spice to the whole volunteering experience and contributes immensely towards personal growth. The researchers recognized that volunteering is a very valuable avenue for developing communication skills and building interpersonal relations.

Another major benefit arising from student volunteerism, according to the research, is enhanced self-esteem. Volunteers are often exposed to different situations that provide both a challenge and a boost to their confidence. The researchers found this in turn builds a much stronger image of the self, thereby, confirming that volunteerism is one pathway through which personal growth and enhanced self-esteem can be achieved.

Another important revelation is being responsive to the community needs. The readiness to answer the call for service in various ministries echoes a volunteers' being responsive. According to the researchers, being responsive to the community needs is a hallmark of committed volunteers and forms the basis upon which successful volunteer activities are developed.

Despite all the rewarding aspects related to volunteerism, the study found challenges that involved student volunteers of CMIA. One is time constraint, and this is because balancing academics and volunteer commitments almost always resulted in conflicts. Researchers have found out that effective time management and the ability to prioritize are very good coping strategies to help them get over this challenge.

Another major challenge is the of demotivation, mostly caused by overwhelming tasks and lack of recognition. In dealing with this challenge, the researchers realized that maintaining motivation and enthusiasm requires strategies such as collaborative assistance and creation of a supportive volunteer environment. Additionally, this poor participation of some volunteers generally lowered the group's performance and morale. The researchers know that it is important to engage people at low levels of participation to prevent frustration and demotivation of active volunteers. In this respect, collaborative efforts and supportive leadership were identified as mitigating strategies for this challenge.

Especially in volunteer selection, large amounts of uncertainty may be involved, particularly in task selection for volunteers who are involved in multiple different ministries. One can learn from these research findings that mechanisms prioritizing needs and relevant tasks and coping with such uncertainties through foresight are quite effective to ensure the completion of tasks efficiently.

This study is, therefore, important in bringing out the complex nature of volunteering among students at NDMU. The researchers became aware of intrinsic motivation, diverse involvement, time management, interpersonal relationships, enhancement of self-esteem, and self-availability that shape the experience of volunteers. Besides, they recognized the reality of challenges facing volunteers and the essence of efficient coping strategies. The research aims at increasing the effectiveness and satisfaction of student-volunteers in a manner that serves personal and societal growth through committed and well-supported volunteerism.

Conclusions

The research on the experiences of Campus Ministry student-volunteers at Notre Dame of Marbel University has greatly enriched the

literature on important areas in student-volunteerism. The research spells out a nuanced understanding of the enriching and challenging dimensions of volunteer experiences and gives valuable insights into how these can be optimized. A number of implications and recommendations have been advanced based on the findings of this study to help increase the effectiveness and satisfaction level of student-volunteers.

At the heart of student-volunteerism is intrinsic motivation—a desire to serve, to help out, and to render one's positive contributions. Intrinsic motivation is that fundamental driving force for effective volunteerism, as reflected in the research. Universities and volunteer organizations, therefore, have to provide an enabling environment that supports the values and interests of volunteers to boost their intrinsic motivation. Such programs will offer opportunities for activities that resonate with their passions and increase their commitment to the cause and deepen satisfaction. To this, recognizing and celebrating volunteers can further solidify their sense of purpose—fostering a more profound connection to the work as well as continued engagement.

The different volunteer activities that the study highlighted bring richness to the volunteer experience. Students are involved in various roles within the many ministries that range from catechism to choir, all making unique contributions towards the community. To fully capture this diversity, it should be the case that universities provide a broad spectrum of volunteer opportunities, ones that will meet varied interests and skills. This can only be possible if institutions foster volunteer engagement in building all-round skills by offering the students platforms to try a variety of roles. Participation in several activities will give volunteers an appreciation for the span of their impact, hence, reinforcing commitment to the community.

Effective time management is a critical element in balancing school and volunteering commitments. This study, thus, emphasizes effective time management techniques in balancing varied responsibilities of volunteers. Higher learning institutions should, therefore, avail time management strategies resources through workshops, seminars, goal setting, task prioritization, and schedule planning. More flexible volunteer opportunities may also be offered that match the students' academic schedules, therefore, not conflicting with them. By empowering volunteers with such skills, institutions can be more capable of multitasking.

In this regard, the creation of interpersonal relationships through volunteerism was noted as a major advantage. Therefore, the creation of strong social bonds is linked to a more fulfilling volunteering experience. In order to realize this, institutions of higher learning, in collaboration with volunteer bodies, should try as much as possible to give students numerous opportunities that enable them to work together and interact with other members of society from different backgrounds. Therefore, arranging team-building activities, networking opportunities, and social events will probably help in building relations that would finally lead to an excellent volunteer experience. This can foster mentorship and peer support in volunteer programs to develop key skills in communication and build lasting bridges for students.

It finds that the act of volunteering actually increases one's self-esteem and personal growth. On the basis of this development, volunteer programs need to involve meaningful feedback, recognition, and skill-enhancing opportunities. In such a supportive environment, volunteers feel recognized by their efforts and have a chance to engage in opportunities for personal growth, which helps boost confidence and self-image. Further, offering some leadership roles and responsibilities helps increase their professional and personal development, hence enhancing their volunteering experience.

Issues that the student-volunteers face, such as time constraints, poor participation, uncertainties on selection of tasks, and demotivation, are brought out in the research work. To counteract these problems, solutions well-targeted by the universities and the volunteer organizations ought to be presented. In so doing, they need to offer training in time management and prioritization to enable volunteers to set balance in academics and volunteering. Realistic goal setting with efficient time management practices should be encouraged to avoid conflicts and enhance productivity.

Moreover, they should provide an environment where volunteers can help each other and distribute responsibilities. Introducing projects based on teams and allowing peers to help one another can solve the problem of ineffective participation and enhance the group's performance. In addition, they need to provide a motivational environment by appreciating volunteers' contribution. Demonstrate less—feedback, celebrate achievements, and make volunteers feel important to keep them enthusiastic and committed. This means they also need to establish policies and systems concerning task allocation to eliminate some amount of uncertainty. In this way, volunteers can organize themselves much better if there are clear expectations given to them and some relevant tasks to be prioritized.

Taking everything into account, the intrinsic motivation of students, diverse roles, time management, interpersonal relationships, self-esteem, and effective coping strategies are identified in this research as central factors that go toward defining the volunteer experience among students. Adoption of the recommended strategies to address the identified challenges will enable universities and volunteer organizations to increase the effectiveness and satisfaction derived from student volunteers. This is how more effective and rewarding volunteer experiences relevant to personal and social growth are engendered.

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